

ASPECTS REGARDING THE POSSIBILITIES OF INCREASING THE QUALITY AND MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN ROMANIA IN THE POST-PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

Purpose – This article aims to present some aspects regarding the possibilities of increasing the quality of the educational system.

Methodology/approach - The methodology adopted consists in identifying methods of analysis and quantification of the possible quality to be applied in an educational system at any level (primary, secondary, pre-university, university and post-university).

Findings – Among these methods, Quality Function Deployment (QFD), break-even method (or critical point method, or dead center, or Break-Even) are presented and analyzed.

Research limitations/implications – The limitations of the research carried out and implicitly, the future research directions consist in finding concrete ways of applying the methods of analysis and quantification of the quality and management of the educational system in Romania in the post-pandemic period. Furthermore, the latest research aims at identifying a set of new methods meant to quantify the quality of the management of the educational system.

Practical implications – The importance of the specificity of the organizational culture (the pre-existing cultural elements at the beginning of the process, the flexibility to bring new values and quality specific norms) was highlighted for the efficiency of the quality of an educational system.

Originality/value – The originality of this article consists in identifying the possibilities of using methods and techniques to increase quality in an educational system.

Key words: management, quality, educational system.

Introduction

The new requirements that foreshadow the future of quality also imply organizational changes through the development of a quality-oriented organizational culture. These changes must be planned, participatory and negotiated (Luta and Ioana, 2021)

The implementation of a quality management system and implicitly its audit are directly conditioned by the specifics of the organizational culture, by the pre-existing cultural elements at the beginning of the process, by the flexibility to bring new values and norms specific to quality.

Having a quality system in the organization is a proof of an efficient management, of a management oriented towards cultural values that implies quality as a fundamental factor of progress. Quality culture is a system of values that exists in an organizational environment that is oriented towards maintaining and continuously improving quality.

The common characteristics of organizations with a favorable climate for quality culture are:

- employees are equally involved and authorized;

- the team is at the core of the activity: managers are equally employed and involved; no responsibility is delegated.

Sufficient resources are allocated, where and when needed, to ensure continuous quality improvement;

- the promotion system and rewards encourage the contribution to continuous quality improvement;
- feedback from customers is actively taken in order to continuously improve quality;
- suppliers and customers are treated as partners;
- there is a value system based on high performance standards for management and human resources, for products / services made;
- communicates continuously, openly;
- continuous evaluation and improvement is practiced

The characteristics of an organization with an unfavorable climate for quality culture are:

- the hostile environment determined by the usual managers to give orders from an isolated position makes it impossible to move towards total quality;
- there are fluctuations of the management members;
- the transition to total quality takes time;
- most of the actions started or of the declared ideas are abandoned;
- employees are not open to the idea of internal partnership based on mutual support and teamwork;
- there is no communication, transparency, receptivity;
- there is no concern for quality and satisfaction of customer requirements

Strategic quality management (MSC) is the new culture at the highest levels of the organization. Its introduction requires initiative and change from senior managers and personal involvement.

Quality is addressed to the people of the organization both as a whole and individually. It involves taking responsibility and total quality management - TQM (Total Quality Management). TQM involves change management (Luta et al, 2021).

The term "Total Quality Management" is used (in English) by almost all specialists and usually means total quality management. Taken in a broader and deeper sense, it also means "total quality management" or "total quality in the management process". In another interpretation it would mean the integration of quality in the different spheres of the management process, ie in finance, sales, marketing, distribution, human resources management, production, public relations, services, etc.

The purpose of managerial activities is to find ways to lead so that the result is a quality product. TQM aims to achieve long-term success by customer satisfaction, based on the participation of all members of the organization in the process of improving technologies, products and services and the organizational climate in which they operate. TQM was used to describe the Japanese style of management, applied to improve quality; the international market has led companies around the world to adopt TQM.

Methods of study, analysis and quantification of quality applicable in the educational system

Studies on the quality of education such as the IEA (Education Assessment Indicators) and international surveys conducted by the OECD (PISA surveys), UNESCO (Education for All) or the European Union (research undertaken by its specialized agencies: Eurostat, Eurydice, ETF and Cedefop) support the use of indicators to meet the requirements of:

- quality assurance in education;
- measuring school progress;
- comparison with the help of common strategies (indicators and reference standards);

In order to identify the problems to be solved, the structuring of ideas and the identification of possible solutions, along with classical techniques and tools, modern tools have been taken from the sphere of management or marketing. They are applied for three main purposes (Luta et al, 2021):

- identifying the important problems to be solved and their causes: the relationship diagram and the tree diagram;
- establishing solutions for solving problems: matrix diagram and tree diagram;
- determining the concrete program meant to solve the problems: PERT diagram and decision diagram.

A method used in planning the quality of products and services: Quality Function Deployment (QFD) aims to eliminate possible errors that may occur throughout the process, even before designing a new product or service.

This method meets customer requirements and gives the manufacturer or service provider the opportunity to design this market-oriented product or service. QFD meets the requirements of customers, the entire approach is based on information obtained from customers, in support of product design (by product we mean possible services provided) based on customer needs. The method is complex and has been developed to maximize customer satisfaction through various techniques and methods.

The QFD method takes into account both expressed and unexpressed customer wishes, translating customer requirements into product features. QFD focuses on providing added value. The customer has the opportunity to express different degrees of importance, or utility, that he would like the product or service to include. This is especially important because an enterprise, or institution, must provide a product that is in demand by the market. The working process of the method is complex, starting with the identification of customer requirements, the last phase of the process being product design (Ioana, 2016).

The modern methods of quality management that are used prior to QFD analysis are the affinity diagram, Gemba, the Kano model and Voice of the customer. The mentioned techniques aim at identifying the clients' requirements, so that they can be integrated in the design process, or adapting the product / service to the market requirements. The QFD method allows the identification of possible future directions of action and the integration of the above mentioned instruments.

The QFD method was developed by the Japanese Yoji Akao. It defines QFD as "a method for developing a design quality aimed at satisfying the consumer and then translating the consumer's demands into design targets and major quality assurance points to be used throughout the production stage".

- For a service, the definition of a QFD could be formulated as follows: "a system and procedures that help plan and develop services and ensure that they meet or exceed customer expectations."
- The purpose of the QFD method can be expressed as follows:
- Quality, by the fact that the client's wishes are transferred to the final product;
- Function, by the fact that all organizational units work together;
- Deployment, to define in more precise units all the necessary activities, which must be measured and controlled.

The QFD method was first applied in 1974 to Toyota in Japan. Quality specialists Makabe (Japan) and D. Clausing (USA) have developed a simplified method called "House of Quality" which consists of a graphical support consisting of six matrices (Luta et al, 2021):

- matrix of customer requirements;
- matrix of technical characteristics;
- connection matrix;
- correlation matrix;
- technical evaluation matrix;
- customer satisfaction assessment matrix.

The method can be adapted depending on the approach of the research and the expected result, there is the possibility of integrating in the analysis all the matrices, or only some of them.

If several QFD analyzes are performed in parallel, a concatenated analysis of all QFD analyzes can be performed, through statistical calculation programs. If there are conflicts in the QFD analysis, in order to resolve them, the TRIZ method (Theory of inventive problem solving) can still be applied. In the development of a product / service there is a need to determine the customer's requirements in order to integrate them properly in the design of the product / service. Determining the customer's requirements in designing a product / service is crucial.

The methods of sampling the client's requirements are:

- Application of a pre-defined questionnaire (Gemba worksheets); the method has the disadvantage that that client could be influenced by the pre-defined criteria in making decisions.
- Offering the possibility for that customer to define for himself the characteristics of the product he would be interested in; the disadvantage of the method refers to the obtaining of results irrelevant for the undertaken research.

To complete the work steps, a special diagram called "House of Quality" is used as a graphic support for this method. In figure 1 we present the structure of the quality house.

Figure 1. The structure of the quality house

The quality house consists of six matrices: the matrix of customer requirements, the matrix of technical characteristics, the matrix of connection, the matrix of correlation, the matrix of technical evaluation and the matrix of evaluation from a market point of view.

In applying the method it turned out that the most difficult thing is to complete the matrix of customer requirements, because it requires a large amount of data and information, which come from different sources. The requirements of the clients related to the product / service of the enterprise are registered within this matrix as well as the degree of importance given to them by the client (Ioana et al, 2021).

The matrix of technical characteristics contains the requirements of the manufacturer / provider of products and services, more precisely it contains the characteristics of the product / service that must be provided by him in order for the product to meet the requirements of the customer.

The connection matrix forms the central area of the diagram within which the connection between the customer's requirements and the technical characteristics of the product / service is highlighted. Within this matrix, the customer's requirements are practically "translated" into technical characteristics of the

product / service. This matrix represents the central area of the diagram, because non-conformities can be identified within it, before the product / service is designed.

The correlation matrix is located at the top of the diagram, which shows the interaction between the technical characteristics. If these interactions are identified in a timely manner, the product / service provider can save a significant amount of resources during product planning. These interactions, or correlations, can be positive (+), or negative (-), but other scales are possible, such as: strongly positive, positive, negative, strongly negative, neutral, etc.

The evaluation matrix of the product / service in relation to the market and its requirements is positioned on the right side of the diagram. In order to complete this matrix, a market research is needed. The importance of each requirement and possible suggestions for improvement can also be established.

The product / service evaluation matrix from a technical point of view is located at the bottom of the diagram. It establishes the importance of each technical feature in meeting customer requirements.

Another method of analysis and quantification of quality possible to be applied in the educational system is the method of profitability threshold (or the method of critical point, or dead center, or Break-Even).

The break-even method is an important method in the analysis of product profitability and profitability on the whole activity, both in the phase of designing new productive capacities, of forecasting the activity, and of analyzing the use of existing production capacities. Figure 2 shows the graphical representation of the break-even method (Ioana et al, 2019).

Figure 2. The graphical representation of the break-even method

Particular attention must be paid to the situation in the "profit above plan" area (profit area above expected) because the situation in this area for an extended period can lead to negative economic mechanisms (inflation, overproduction, etc.).

Discussion and conclusions

The analysis and quantification of the educational system quality at any level (primary, gymnasium, pre-university, university, postgraduate) has a special importance for identifying the ways and methods of increasing the quality specific to this field.

The specificity of organizational culture (pre-existing cultural elements at the beginning of the process, the flexibility to bring new values and quality-specific norms) is very important for streamlining the quality of an educational system.

One possible method to use to increase the quality of an educational system is Quality Function Deployment (QFD). This method aims to eliminate possible errors that may occur throughout the process, even before designing a new product or service.

Also, the use of the break-even method (or the critical point method, or the break-even method, or Break-Even) can lead to the efficiency of the quality of an educational system. The analysis through economic and managerial mechanisms of the situation in one of the 3 distinct areas of the method (area of losses, area of expected profit, area of profit over expected) allows the identification of the most efficient methods to increase the quality of the educational system.

Not only will future research in this field aim at finding concrete ways of applying the methods of analysis and quantification of the quality and management of the educational system in Romania in the post-pandemic period, but also at developing new methods of quantifying the management quality of the educational system.

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